

10,000 ha in 1976. In Cuu-Long, 5,000 ha of the main rice crop were infested in 1975 and more than 6,000 ha in 1980.

Infested rice areas in the Mekong Delta seemed to increase gradually. The most common local rice varieties such as Trang-Lun, Trang-Tep, Tau-huong, Nang-Tay-Dum, Nang-Tay C, Tau-Nuc, Trung-Hung, Chau-Hang-Vo, Chet-xanh, and Ba-Thiet were affected seriously. Field surveys of 200 local varieties showed that none escaped. The disease also occurred in transplanted areas on short growth duration varieties such as IR5, IR30, IR36, and IR9129-192-2-3-5.

The disease was most severe in months of heavy rainfall, or high field water level. Of the three rice crops in the Mekong Delta, the main crop (June-December) suffered great damage, the He-thu crop (April-August) moderate damage, and the Dong-xuan crop (December-April) little damage. ■

Distribution of rice stem nematode disease in the Mekong Delta 1975-80. University of Cantho, Hau-Giang, Vietnam.

Effect of length of treatment and fungicide concentration on seed germination and incidence of foot rot disease of rice

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Most rice seeds are infested with the fungus *Fusarium moniliforme* (foot rot) which causes preemergence and post-emergence damping-off of seedlings. To promote germination, seeds in wetbed nurseries usually are soaked in water for 24 hours and kept in wet bags for 2-3 days before sowing. Most seeds are attacked by foot rot during this period. This study was conducted to find the effect of seed treatment period on germination and infection.

The fungicide Ceresan wet (methoxy-ethyl mercury chloride) was used at 0.1 and 0.2% concentrations in water. Rice cultivar Ratna seeds were dipped in the fungicidal solutions for 3-96 hours. Matching bags of seed were dipped in plain water for a control. Seed bags were shaken at intervals during treatment. Germination and foot rot infection of 400 seeds were tested by the blotter method.

Effect of seed immersion and fungicide treatment on germination and foot root incidence in rice cultivar Ratna, Cuttack, India.

Immersion time (h)	Plain water		Concn (%)	Ceresan wet	
	Seed germination (%)	Foot rot infection (%)		Seed germination (%)	Foot rot infection (%)
3	46	6.6	0.1	49	3.8
			0.2	50	2.5
6	58	5.0	0.1	62	3.2
			0.2	54	1.5
12	62	6.0	0.1	71	3.0
			0.2	62	1.2
24	65	5.3	0.1	70	3.0
			0.2	73	0.5
36	66	4.5	0.1	72	2.5
			0.2	74	0.0
48	67	3.3	0.1	70	0.0
			0.2	76	0.0
72	68	4.0	0.1	73	0.0
			0.2	74	0.0
96	64	3.8	0.1	69	0.0
			0.2	74	0.0

Germination percentages were higher for seed soaked in Ceresan (see table). Foot rot infection was controlled when

seeds were immersed in 0.1% Ceresan for 48 hours or longer and in 0.2% solution for 36 hours or longer. ■

Seasonal incidence of brown spot and narrow brown leaf spot in the Thanjavur delta, India

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Seasonal incidence of brown spot (BS) and narrow brown leaf spot (NBLS) was studied for five consecutive cropping seasons 1975-80. Each year, 20 plantings spanning the cropping period